
Competency Framework for Research Data Services in Norway

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Summary

“Competence Framework for Research Data Management in Norway” was a one-year project (autumn 2021 – autumn 2022) (Bibliotekutvikling, 2021) run by the Norwegian node of the Research Data Alliance (RDA-NO) and financed by the National Library of Norway. The purpose of the project was to obtain a concise overview of the competence needs for research data management in the Norwegian higher education sector. Through a combination of surveys and workshops we have uncovered several needs for competence building in research data management as a discipline. This report presents the results of the project. Figure 1 (p. 4) summarizes the framework by grouping and dividing the competence needs into different categories.

Researchers need to have data management support embedded in their research groups, and the role of the library is primarily to coordinate and complement their work. The library has broad experience with best practices and data stewardship as a researcher support function and makes this expertise available to researchers. This contributes to the continuous changes that are needed to meet the needs of digital research. Research is innovative, and constantly pushing boundaries in search for new findings, which requires that data stewards are familiar with research and able to advise based on the research's premises.

In our recommendations, we emphasize the value of investing in dual expertise and interdisciplinary collaboration. Increasing competence in data stewardship is time-consuming. It is therefore important that the competence is maintained and further developed through permanent positions and continuity in the organisations. Local ownership with national collaborations and coordination are also important to avoid unnecessary bureaucratisation. We therefore encourage the establishment of structures for knowledge exchange within various areas of expertise at the national level and confirm RDA-NO as the appropriate coordinator for such networks.

Based on the study, we make the following recommendations to the management of Norwegian academic libraries and to the education programs that aim to educate or provide training to the data stewards of the future.

Recommendations to the libraries' management

1. Regard research data management as a focus area in the work with open research and research quality.
2. Map the competences internally in the organizations based on the six competence areas described in the framework.
3. Invest in continued education, recruitment, and collaboration to build expertise in the areas that are not currently covered.
4. Invest in disciplinary knowledge and research experience to build up dual expertise in the subject area and data management, respectively.
5. Further develop existing knowledge within subject areas, collection management and metadata in the work with data management.
6. Act as a contact point for data managers who work in the professional environment.
7. Piloting models for data steward positions coordinated by the library based on models from pioneering institutions in the field.
8. Bring in external funding for development of projects that will increase knowledge about data management.
9. Stakeholder support for responsibility for data management locally at the research libraries and collaborate nationally.
10. Participate in international networks and contribute to developments in the field.

Recommendations for the education of data stewards:

1. Establish study subjects based on the competence areas in the framework in regular education programmes.
2. Establish offers for post-graduate education and advanced training based on the six competence areas described in the framework.
3. Coordinate education programmes with courses and certification work from other national and international actors

Competency Framework for research data services

1 Administration

- Policy development
- Strategy development
- Strategic anchoring
- Project management
- Highlight needs
- Apply for funding
- Implementation of policy

4 Ethics and law

- Copyright
- Licensing
- Intellectual property rights
- Privacy and GDPR
- Research ethics
- The Health Research Act
- Contract law

2 Mediation

- Pedagogy
- Instruction
- Presentation
- Communication
- Culture change
- Instruction in guidelines
- Create space for dialogue & learning
- Disclosure of policy

5 Technical skills

- Programming skills
- Software knowledge
- IT security
- Data visualization
- System understanding
- Operation and maintenance of infrastructure

3 Data management

- Data stewardship experience
- Metadata
- Ontologies
- Curation
- Long-term perspective on RDM
- Documentation
- Persistent Identifiers
- Research data as cultural heritage

6 Domain knowledge

- Research experience
- Research methods
- Experience in curation
- Training and Guidance
- Terminology
- Translate between different subjects

Personal skills

- Ability to listen
- Learning from others
- Professional updates

- Exploratory
- Network builder
- Independent

- Cooperation
- Organized
- Patient

Figure 1 Competency Framework for research data services

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Introduction

Extensive work has been done internationally to define and describe the skills needed to deliver good services in research data management. For this project we have chosen to refer to and describe international documents and reports in this field, rather than to duplicate previous work. In addition we have conducted an all-day workshop with 40 participants from large and small institutions in the higher education sector. The documents from both phases of the survey are available via OSF, see Kvale et al. (2022). Input from the workshop helped to describe the Norwegian context and the local specificities that do not appear in the international publications.

A competency framework defines a set of knowledge and skills needed to develop professionally within a given domain (Rivera-Ibarra et al., 2010). By defining the knowledge needs related to data management, the project simplifies the process of identifying needs for skills development. Furthermore, a competence framework can function as a basis for designing educational programmes. Based on this, we make recommendations aimed at the management of university libraries and the educational actors in the field as to how competence in the research data management domain can be raised. The need for training data stewards has previously been highlighted in point 1.5 of the National Strategy for Access and Sharing of Research Data (Ministry of Education and Research, 2017).

The work to create a competence framework for research data management aimed at the Norwegian higher education sector is based on the group's own experiences from the field. We identified the lack of an overview of different types of competence and skills needed to meet demands and needs for better data management in research which was relevant to the Norwegian context. Knowledge of skills needed varies, and this project provided the opportunity to collect and summarize relevant skills while identifying needs and challenges which need to be solved.

Some of the key challenges highlighted in the study were that in order to provide support, one must have both broad and deep expertise in addition to the ability to navigate a complex and evolving landscape. The demand for dual expertise, in the form of subject area knowledge with research experience and competence in data stewardship is significant; this dual expertise is commonly referred to as "boundary spanning" and takes time to acquire (Thompson, 2017). As a translation for the English terms "data steward" or "data manager" we have chosen to use the Norwegian term "datahåndterer". We use it as a general overarching term to denote various types of positions where research data management constitutes the main part of the work, which includes roles such as data manager, data curator, data librarian or data administrator. We have chosen to focus on areas of knowledge rather than divisions and different roles and job types.

We would like to emphasize that it is impossible for one person to know everything regarding research data management and individually meet all demands. The library's tasks in terms of research data can roughly be divided into research support, administration, infrastructure, and teaching and training. In order to fulfill these functions, it is important to have expertise in technical and digital skills, politics and administration, ethics and law, domain knowledge, communication and teaching skills, as well as certain personal qualities.

When we describe the various types of competence needed to work with data management in a research library, we do not expect a single person to know all of this. By outlining the wide spectrum of demanded knowledge, we want to make it easier to express what competence one has, what competence one needs in one's own organization, and what needs to be brought in through external collaborations. When it comes to deciding what expertise to hold, institutions will prioritize differently.

A majority of those who work with research data management in Norwegian academic libraries have research data management as one of several areas of responsibility. Therefore, collaboration and sharing expertise is even more relevant in order to provide comprehensive services to the researchers at their institution. Collaboration with other players at the institution is highlighted as crucial to deliver a good service. There are not enough resources to cover all of the needs related to the sharing and storage of research data in the library, but at the same time the participants at the workshop emphasized a desire to deliver a service that appears holistic to the outside.

To illustrate how we think of the library's role in the work with data management, we have created Figure 2, The library's role in research data management, where we place the library as a hub or mediator of demands and needs that come from financiers, publishers and researchers respectively. This is solved by connecting other resources, resource persons and infrastructure, while emphasizing the library's role as a driving force for development work in the field. It is the competence that is needed to be able to deliver at this junction which we describe further in the competence framework. At certain institutions, this work may be organized differently, but both in Norway and internationally the most common model for research data management is that responsibility for the field is fully or partially assigned to the library (LIBER Europe, 2020b; Swiatek et al., 2020).

Figure 2 The library's role in research data management

Based on the survey, we have set up seven types of competence: administration, mediation, data management, ethics & law, technical skills, domain knowledge and personal skills (Figure 3). These seven competence areas together make up the competence framework, and are reviewed in the next chapter.

Following the presentation of the categories we discuss main challenges related to competence for research data management; competence management and collaboration.

Figure 3 Competence categories within research data management

The competence framework

This chapter presents the content of the seven categories in the competence framework (Figure 3). Certain areas of expertise could fall under several categories; in these cases, we have assigned them to one category. The division into institution-oriented and researcher-oriented competence is not black and white, but intended to illustrate how the library provides services in several directions which to some extent require different competences.

1. Administration

A large portion of the tasks related to data stewardship are administrative and organizational. Getting the management on board and anchoring the work in the organization is essential for the establishment of a mandate, guidelines and policy. Project development, funding, management and evaluation are administrative skills. These are needed to develop the necessary offers and services that facilitate the implementation and compliance of policy. There is also a continuous need for prioritising, collaboration and awareness-raising. This is central to the work of creating a culture change for data management and data sharing with the reuse of data as a goal. This requires good knowledge of your own organization and an understanding of decision-making processes. An overview of requirements and expectations from funders and journals combined with the ability to identify best practices is also considered an administrative competence, while mentoring researchers is described here as a [mediation competence](#).

Leading the data management work requires a good overview of knowledge and skills inside and outside one's own organization and the ability to think long-term and systematically about competence enhancement and competence transfer. Data management and open research are connected and both sides require an open culture of knowledge. A central task is to put the use of data management plans as tools for planning on the agenda (LIBER Europe, 2020a). In order to build up good services, there is a need for good governance through mapping and evaluation of competence development, infrastructure and the extent to which the institution is able to make research data FAIR (LIBER Europe, 2020a, 2020b).

It is also becoming increasingly relevant to raise funding from various sources and to have awareness of the development in the data management domain. This includes seeking funding for projects focused on service development and is linked to the need to test new forms of collaboration and present the library as a relevant actor in the research infrastructure domain (Cox et al., 2017, 2019).

Internationally the libraries have shown an eagerness to establish knowledge hubs in partnership with specialists in metadata and documentation, method and discipline-specific data handling, teaching, IT and more general research advice (Molloy et al., 2021). In such hubs, data management services are embedded to cover the various needs identified in the institution. We also see this trend amongst some of the larger research institutions in Norway. Such collaborations require good organizational skills and the ability to manage and build up a network of experts both inside and outside one's own department (Boserup Thestrup et al., 2020; Swiatek et al., 2020).

Administrative support aimed at researchers can include guidance for funding for data management in internal research projects (Boserup Thestrup et al., 2020). In addition, being a partner in interdisciplinary collaborations with a special responsibility for data stewardship and data practices is a way the library is involved in research projects (LIBER Europe, 2020c).

2. Mediation

As a hub for knowledge related to research data management, the library plays an important role in raising awareness among the relevant actors. Through training and dialogue with the academic community, the research administration, and the IT department, the library makes policy, guidelines and best practices for open science and the FAIR principles visible across the institution (Boserup Thestrup et al., 2020; LIBER Europe, 2017a). It is therefore important that the library stays up-to-date on developments and needs related to data management in academia and in society in general.

An important task is to make researchers aware of the advantages of good data management and open research. Researchers also need to have knowledge of relevant requirements and guidelines, and need awareness regarding the responsibility to make data available to others. Through teaching and consultancy with the researchers, pedagogical skills are essential in order to communicate the how and why of research data management in an effective way. Within research data management, different arguments and considerations are emphasized differently by different actors, the library should listen to the researchers' arguments and avoid introducing additional agendas. Data sharing based on general research ethical principles (The Norwegian National Research Ethics Committees, 2014) is the common platform on which to meet researchers. It is important to build the trust necessary for research data services and good data management practice to become an integrated part of the researcher's workflow. The data manager must be able to convey their knowledge of good practices for data management and encourage the sharing and reuse of open data where possible. Through teaching and dissemination, a culture of FAIR data sharing is built which also inspires young researchers to establish good routines (Boserup Thestrup et al., 2020).

Open research, FAIR principles and guidelines must be incorporated into the curriculum and teaching resources and made relevant to the target groups by using subject-specific terminology and practical examples that users recognize (see [Domain knowledge](#)). The training offered by the libraries should cover basic skills for data management and provide practical information about services and resources relevant to researchers. Being able to convey new knowledge to researchers and by this raising the level of knowledge about data management was also highlighted in the workshop.

As a mediator, one must be able to work both independently and collaboratively with planning, development and execution of courses. There will always be a need to evaluate and incorporate new aspects into courses as best practice for data management changes (Boserup Thestrup et al., 2020; Molloy et al., 2021, p. 6). This requires continuous development of the mediator's competence. It is important to tailor the teaching to the researchers needs and ensure that the training is simple, accessible and practically oriented to fit into the researchers' everyday life (Boserup Thestrup et al., 2020). Learning materials and teaching plans should

be tailored for different forms of teaching such as face-to-face, digital or physical lectures, workshops, interactive online resources, or recording of videos and screencasts.

Visibility and promotion of one's own support services are also part of communication skills. For this, one must make use of various relevant channels and platforms to reach the user groups and spread information. To make it easy for researchers to find services, tools and help, it is useful to use simple visual aids and to create user-friendly and easy-to-find websites (Boserup Thestrup et al., 2020).

3. Data management support

The project has identified a need for expertise in support of data stewardship in various phases of the research and the research data life-cycles. We have chosen the term data management support to highlight this need. By data management support we mean advanced support for data management, which requires experience from various stages of the data management work. At times, the boundaries between data management support and the other five categories will be unclear, but we still see the need for this category to cover something different from the other five by having a data management perspective on the research process.

In the planning of a research project, knowledge about the design and quality assurance of data management plans, including guidance in the use of data management planning tools, will be relevant (Schmidt & Shearer, 2016). If there is a need to reuse data, expertise in retrieval is needed to identify relevant data archives and mechanisms for data discovery (Bishop et al., 2019). Here, searching skills from traditional literature search were emphasized in the workshop. In addition good citation practices for data and the use of persistent identifiers were highlighted as relevant skills. Reuse of data from other sources may also require [legal expertise](#) where there is a need for rights clearances.

Furthermore, competence is needed to guide researchers in the application of standardized methods, advice in the management of software (software management) and the choice of metadata standards (LIBER Europe, 2020b; Schmidt & Shearer, 2016). Here [domain knowledge](#) is also relevant. Some research projects will also need active assistance with data management on request; a need that is described in more detail under [competence management and collaboration](#). Data stewardship support must also be able to offer expertise on open research more generally and be up-to-date on various aspects of open research, as well as have a comprehensive understanding of what the FAIR principles entail in practice for various research domains (LIBER Europe, 2017).

Knowledge on how to prepare data for archiving and bringing in the long-term perspective is also emphasized (Schmidt & Shearer, 2016), this also includes competence in the selection of data for archiving. Again, there will be some overlap with the need for [domain knowledge](#). It is also important to have experience with preparing documentation of the data (e.g. in readme files) and a holistic view of how to make data reusable (Schmidt & Shearer, 2016). In connection with the archiving of data, people who work with data management support must be able to offer advice on how to find and select an appropriate archive. This involves having knowledge of requirements, licensing, degree of curation and standards for metadata at

various archive services (LIBER Europe, 2020b; Schmidt & Shearer, 2016). The ability to adopt metadata standards, schemas, formats, identifiers, domain ontologies and vocabularies are other aspects highlighted here (Schmidt & Shearer, 2016). Expertise in and experience with archiving is required to assist researchers in archiving in various repositories and archives, including experience with reviewing documentation, metadata and formats in connection with archiving (LIBER Europe, 2020b; Swiatek et al., 2020).

Data-specific archival expertise is also required for the curation and preservation of archived data (Horstmann & Cox, n.d.; LIBER Europe, 2020a). It includes competence to ensure interoperability and authenticity of archived data, code, and associated documentation in relevant data archives while at the same time facilitating access and retrieval by ensuring at all times that standards are up to date and that the material is stable (LIBER Europe, 2017b). In addition to expertise in data management, expertise in the further development of routines, standards and formats including metadata standards is necessary (Boserup Thestrup et al., 2020). Data management is a large field in constant change; an understanding of and commitment to implementing changes by linking the research front and data support service closely together is important (Schmidt & Shearer, 2016). Contributing to the development of the field through participation in national and international forums such as EOSC, LIBER, FORCE11, RDA is necessary to develop and use new knowledge in the field.

4. Ethical and legal competence

The ethical and legal challenges associated with managing research data are many and complex. Among the legal challenges we find issues of rights and privacy. Ethical competence often involves finding good balances between different considerations. When the issues are new, which will always be the case in work with ground-breaking research and technology, ethics can be used to arrive at solid solutions that balance various considerations. At the same time, researchers and research operates in an international world and therefore often have to navigate different legislation and ethical norms. Knowledge of research ethics and various ethical norms is necessary to be able to make trade-offs that respect legislation, while at the same time making it possible for research to be carried out as openly as possible.

Copyright and privacy are the two legal areas we most often encounter when working with the sharing of research data, and in this area there is a need for basic knowledge to provide guidance to researchers and refer them to expert services when needed (Schmidt & Shearer, 2016). In order to provide support for the management of personal data, one must have basic knowledge of the Norwegian Personal Data Act (The Norwegian Personal Data Act, 2018). This includes knowledge of the basic privacy principles, grounds for processing, what constitutes special categories of data, and what applies as personal data versus anonymous data. The support staff in the library can in part rely on external expertise, but close dialogue with the data protection officer and legal advisers at the institution is important. Furthermore, there is a need for a good knowledge of the Norwegian Data Protection Authority, the national ethics committees, regional committees for medical and healthcare research ethics, privacy services provided by Sikt, and other relevant resources.

Researchers experience the balancing of privacy and research as challenging in the context of requirements for data sharing (Kvale & Darch, 2022). Knowledge of archive solutions for data that needs protection is required. The same applies to guidance in the formulation of consent forms for the reuse of data from people. Proper anonymization requires in-depth knowledge of the project in question. In curation work, it is nevertheless necessary to be able to recognize personal data and, if necessary, make researchers aware that anonymisation is difficult to achieve. Here, ethical assessments and experience are crucial to finding good solutions for how research and privacy can coexist.

Another advisory task related to data sharing is to assist researchers in making good decisions regarding licensing. Knowledge of national recommendations, for example from the licensing committee (Forskningsrådet, 2021) is necessary. Knowledge of copyright regulations to assist researchers using copyrighted material in their research is also in demand. Where there are inquiries about more complex rights challenges, including shared rights or patenting, researchers need more specialized advice regarding legislation and institutional requirements if they are to make sound assessments and choices for their research.

5. Technical skills

Technical skills are essential in order to deliver targeted support services and help researchers in navigating existing systems and resources. In addition, technical skills are central to communicating effectively with partners. Several existing frameworks point out that different roles in data management support require different degrees of technical skills, from basic understanding to some highly specialized experts (see competence matrix from mapping in (L. Kvale et al., 2022). FAIR Competence Framework for Higher Education (Demchenko et al., 2021) is a document we recommend for a thorough overview of relevant technical skills.

A basic understanding of IT architecture, IT security, data storage and transfer, file formats, database structures and calculation operations is a prerequisite for providing good guidance to the researchers. This is also useful when collaborating with IT departments and infrastructures to implement the appropriate IT infrastructure for storage and documentation of data management during the research process while at the same time facilitating FAIR archiving of data (LIBER Europe, 2017 , 2020).

Supporting researchers in processing, archiving and reusing data can be done across disciplines, e.g. need for code-based data cleaning, formatting, analysis, databases and visualization (e.g. experience using Python, R, Jupyter Notebooks), version control (git), use of container software/controlled environments, knowledge of semantic web, data exchange formats (e.g. XML, JSON), metadata models, text mining and markup/markdown (LIBER Europe, 2020; Molloy et al., 2021; Swiatek et al., 2020). Experience using command-line tools and basic programming skills are required for handling and curating certain types of datasets. Many technical skills are closely linked to subject-specific skills such as e.g. use of certain software.

Research data services also experience a demand for skills that do not have an obvious place among the researcher support functions in the organization and that are at the intersection

between practical tools and methods, for example transcription tools, statistical methods and various software-specific skills. In order to ensure access to broad technical expertise, it is appropriate to have an overview of internal and external expertise and resources, and possibilities for cooperation between the University Library and other units with expertise in research infrastructure.

6. Domain knowledge

Knowledge of professional culture, professional terms and preferably experience with one's own previous and/or ongoing research is valuable in several contexts. One of these is when there is a need for knowledge and understanding of subject-specific methods and data types when teaching, advising, and curating. The material can then be made more relevant through the use of subject-specific terminology and practical examples that the researchers recognize (Molloy & Snow, 2012). Subject-specific skills also make it easier to engage in dialogue on concrete cases within the subject area, including providing examples and being able to point to services and resources that are relevant. Subject area knowledge often acts as a bridge-builder between data management and research and helps to link these together.

In tutorials and during curation, domain knowledge is a prerequisite for being able to quickly understand the content of a data set, related research articles, methods and software. It is also necessary to be able to identify subject-specific data archives where the data can be made reusable in line with the FAIR principles. This includes knowledge of academically relevant file formats, metadata standards, and current ontologies/vocabularies and annotations.

In the workshop, it was emphasized that many people experience a lack of the subject-specific competence that researchers expect and would like to be able to refer to. An important move is to put together teams of people with different backgrounds and different approaches to data and methods in order to be able to meet different researchers with a broad understanding of research data management. In order to build up such teams, subject managers at the library are likely to be involved.

In addition to this, there is also a need to draw in data management expertise from other parts of the organization and from external environments. Such networks are important for being able to seek advice and make referrals. The need to support the development of several strong domain-specific expert communities is highlighted. Professional expertise environments and infrastructures such as ELIXIR¹, CLARIN² and CESSDA³ complement the library by offering subject-specific advice and services for data management.

7. Personal characteristics

It is important that those who work with support for data management have good collaboration skills, are good at networking, and are able to build up and facilitate arenas for

¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/>

² <https://www.clarin.eu/>

³ <https://www.cessda.eu/>

collaboration. Establishing a network with data stewards who work in professional environments is an example, but networks for curation and professional updating are also necessary (Teperek et al., 2022). You must be a team player and an ambassador for a rapidly developing domain which requires steadfastness and determination. The importance of clarifying the purpose of cooperation and setting clear common goals in order to succeed in cooperation is also emphasized.

The researchers are the most important partners in achieving better data management, and respect for research on the premises of the research is important (L. Kvale, 2021). You must be able to listen to experts and let researchers take an active role. It is also important to be able to recognize that small improvements are better than none and to make good and broad compromises.

In addition to being good at networking, it is important to have other interpersonal skills such as the ability to create trust and a safe environment for dialogue and a good learning environment. It is necessary to be able to be patient, reflective and diplomatic both in order to create good grounding with management and a dialogue with research environments (Swiatek et al., 2020).

Support for data management and curation of datasets can also be painstaking work that requires one to be analytical and have an eye for detail. Data management is a large field, with many details, which makes it extra important to be structured and have good control of planning and time management (LIBER Europe, 2020a).

In the work with data management, new thinking is required - to reflect and contribute to research and development in the field. This requires a person who is self-driven and a seeker of knowledge and who enjoys familiarizing themselves with new topics and keeping up-to-date professionally. It is necessary to look to other institutions and organisations, nationally and internationally, be inspired and get involved in the developments that are taking place and implement changes in one's own institution.

Competence management and collaboration

Competence in data stewardship is often vulnerable because few resources are allocated to the tasks. The majority of those who work with data management have this as one of many areas of responsibility, which makes collaboration across units and institutions extra important. In addition, the survey has highlighted that competence in research data management is specialist competence and not something off-the-shelf. An understanding of research, as well as good professional networks, is absolutely essential to be able to offer good solutions for data management - these are skills that are largely built up from the ground up internally within the organisations.

The university management is highlighted as an important partner in creating both anchorage and drive for the work, and good dialogue and understanding is important. The research administration is an important partner with its expertise in applications, application processes, and financial and legal issues. Here, the need for data management plans or courses can be

captured and communicated at an early stage. The IT departments are important partners in the delivery of technology and support for software, storage, data security and analysis.

Privacy representatives at the institutions have in-depth knowledge of privacy, health research and research ethics, but have little capacity to take in the multitude of different questions related to law and ethics in research. For those institutions that use Sikt Personal Protection Services, it is the case that the researchers have most and perhaps only contact with Sikt in connection with the management of personal data in their projects. In the input to the workshop there was a call for an opportunity to gain insight into correspondence as an advisor on data management in the dialogue between researcher and Sikt. The library's role in these collaborations will be for the good data steward who has an overview of the whole, and refers to the right special services and follows up on the whole in the need for data management - it is not just privacy assessments or storage capacity that is needed, but a more holistic and comprehensive planning and follow-up to make the breadth of research data as FAIR as possible.

The research support staff is dependent on good national investigations of legal ambiguities and clear recommendations. Such studies are important tools for those who provide support for data management to guide researchers to make good decisions. Nationally, partnerships between organizations such as the Norwegian RDA node and BOTT are important for investigating and recommending, and as these are instigated by the institutions, the researchers' perspectives and needs are taken care of in the best possible way.

Service providers in the national landscape are also important collaboration partners, but at the same time it is important that the institutions themselves have the freedom to set the conditions for collaboration based on actual needs. Knowledge of and dialogue with international networks in one's own professional field, sometimes linked to archives, is also important to safeguard the professional environment. RDA also represents a valuable international network in the field that largely embraces the breadth and variety of needs and challenges.

Professionalization of support staff has been identified as an important step to advance the archiving of FAIR research data (EOSC Executive Board., 2021; Molloy et al., 2021). An important group in data management are data stewards who work in larger research projects.

There is a need for a coordinated responsibility to ensure that the expertise of these resource persons is retained and passed on within the own organisation. Challenges related to data stewards today include, among other things, a lack of competence. Furthermore, there are often large drop-outs and a large turnover of people as positions are often temporary. Another problem is the lack of recognition of the special competence required; data stewards are recruited for their research competence and then build up competence in data management. At the same time, this group is rarely recognized as researchers in the groups they belong to (Teperek et al., 2022). Competent and motivated support personnel with expertise in both subject areas and data management, so-called dual expertise, are of great importance, both for sharing data in projects and for supporting cultural changes from within the research environments.

Data stewards from research groups who took part in the workshop stated that it is demanding to be a partner in a project while at the same time having data management responsibility and

emphasize the importance of having colleagues with supplementary expertise that they can draw on as sparring partners and for knowledge exchange. The library and national networks such as the Norwegian RDA node can thus have an important role as a network builder for data stewards by facilitating the exchange of experience and contact across professional environments.

An overview or coordination of various initiatives for networks may also be necessary. Many projects will need their own data stewards; the libraries can act as a hub for these. In this way, it is possible to capture what expertise exists around the organization and to convey new knowledge. The library can also act as a contact point for research groups that wish to employ data stewards, e.g. in the context of a larger externally funded project. This is something we see examples of in the Netherlands, among others (Teperek et al., 2018, 2022). Here there is a need for more knowledge about which models are suitable for the Norwegian HE landscape, which account for the size of institutions, job categories and career paths for data stewards. There is currently too little knowledge of the field for us to make clear recommendations; the consequences of data stewards being often employed in temporary positions should therefore be better investigated.

Conclusion

Library staff act as resource persons focused on following developments in the field and ensuring that knowledge of changes and clarifications related to data management that occur nationally and internationally reaches the professional communities and assisting where professional support is not in place. Despite good planning, research projects will encounter new and unknown challenges in terms of data management. Proximity to research must be the basis for creating an offer of a service that reflects the needs of researchers. The library's role is as a contact and hub at the institution, which requires a broad network and good knowledge of a number of areas of expertise. Competence framework for research data management helps to highlight the breadth and depth of the competence needed, based on the current situation. At the same time, it represents a snapshot of the needs identified in the current situation. In order to keep the competence framework up to date, there will be a need for new surveys that capture changes.

It is necessary to highlight the importance of broad and deep expertise in addition to the need for collaboration for decision-makers in the institutions. The need for collaboration and professional networks is strong. This applies to both researcher-related data stewards at the institutions; subject network in computer science nationally with international links; and collaboration within the various areas of expertise. Projects such as the "Curator network for FAIR research data"⁴ are important for establishing lines for knowledge exchange across institutions in a way that is also adapted to the smaller institutions. We also find a great need to investigate models for career paths for data stewards in various job types. Many in this group are experts in several fields at the same time while balancing many roles, and are often in temporary positions with different job categories.

⁴ <https://bibliotekutvikling.no/prosjektbank/prosjekt/kuratornettverk-for-fair-forskingsdata/>

Keeping up-to-date on international models for data management support is time-consuming; the field is therefore dependent on established networks for competence development. We also see that the larger universities contribute to raising the breadth of institutions by initiating studies, establishing infrastructure and holding courses that are open to outsiders. It is important, but at the same time resource-intensive, to deal with what is happening internationally and test what suits the Norwegian context.

Furthermore, we would like to point out the need to engage in dialogue with national actors in library development about contributions to raise the level of competence in data stewardship in the sector.

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The project group 25 October 2022.

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